

A Taxonomic Survey on Vespid and Sphecic Wasps (Hymenoptera: Vespidae and Sphecidae) of Malappuram and kozhikode Districts in Kerala.

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Abstract

Hymenoptera is one of the four great orders of insects and includes more than 100000 species. This order is divided into two main suborders: Symphyta and Apocrita. Wasps are predators of almost all insect larvae, which attack forest, agriculture, and plantation crops and are also good pollinators and play a vital role in the ecosystem. The present study dealt with biosystematics of vespid and sphecic wasps of Malappuram and Kozhikode districts of Kerala state. A checklist of collected vespid and sphecic wasps were prepared. A total of 38 wasps were collected in 2 families. Collected 38 specimens are contained 23 species in two families. A total of 18 species of vespids under 11 genera in 3 subfamilies (Eumeninae, Polistinae, and Vespinae) were reported in this study. The majority of vespid wasps are reported from subfamily Eumeninae. Vespids were mainly obtained from the Malappuram district. 5 species of sphecic wasps under 4 genera in 3 subfamilies are reported from Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. 3 sphecic subfamilies reported in this study are Ammophilinae, Sceliphrinae, and Sphecinae. Among collected specimens, female wasps were more in number compared with males.

Keywords : Taxonomy, vespid wasp, mud dauber wasp, Malappuram, Kozhikode, Kerala

Introduction

The family Vespidae is a moderately large family with more than 5000 species worldwide. Adult vespid wasps are generally predominantly black or brown but are often extensively marked with yellow or white. They are commonly known as the potter wasps, paper wasps, hover wasps, hornets, yellow jackets, etc. which are mainly predatory insects. Sphecidae is a cosmopolitan family of solitary wasps, which includes mud dauber wasps, sand wasps, and other thread-waisted wasps. Globally, it consists of 793 species in five subfamilies (Ammophilinae, Chloriontinae, Sceliphrinae Sphecinae, and Stangeellinae) and 19 genera (Pulawski, 2019). They have cylindrical gastral petiole and hindwing with a large jugal lobe, containing an anal vein (Bohart & Menke, 1976). Wasps are predators of almost all insect larvae, which attack forest, agriculture and plantation crops and have skill in making a variety of nests. As they are venomous insects their study also has an importance in public health science.

Our study covered the human-inhabited, paddy field, forest, and hill areas of selected regions in Malappuram and Kozhikode districts, Kerala. Most of the wasps were collected from the Malappuram district. Some publications provide taxonomic data of wasps of Kottooli and Thalassery-Dharmadam mangroves of Kerala (Kumar & Rajmohana, 2018) and scoliid, vespid, ampulicid, and sphecid wasps of Madayipara, Kannur (Kumar et al., 2020). But the vespid and sphecid wasps were poorly studied in Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. It reveals the need of the present study.

Materials and Methods

Wasps were collected from selected regions of Malappuram and Kozhikode districts, which include hill areas, forests, and paddy fields. Collection sites from Malappuram were Adyanpara, PSMO college campus, Arimbra, Thadapparamb, Muchirikkadu, and Mini Ooty. Arippara, Muthappanpuzha, Vellarimala, and Koorottupara were the selected regions from the Kozhikode district.

Specimens were collected by using net sweeping and trapping methods. Net sweeping was the most used collection method for this study. Collected wasps were killed using ethyl acetate solution and preserved in 70% alcohol. The specimens were mounted on cards or by inserting standard entomological pins, in such a way that all characters are visible to an observer. Temporary labels were written in the field at the time of specimen collection. After mounting the specimens, permanent labels showing the name of the country, state, date of collection, name of the collector, etc. were added. Sorting and mounting were done under a stereo zoom microscope (Olympus trinocular microscope- CX21i). Images are captured using this stereo zoom microscope with a CMOS 10MP camera and Magnus-Pro software. Some images were also captured with a realme 5s mobile phone by using the ultra-macro lens option. Later the photographs were used for the identification with help of the literature and unidentified specimens were taken into the Zoological Survey of India, Kozhikode for identification.

Result and Discussion

Altogether of 38 wasps were collected in 2 families from selected regions of Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. Collected 38 wasps have contained 23 species under 15 genera in 6 subfamilies of 2 families. A total of 18 species of vespid wasps under 11 genera in 3 subfamilies (Eumeninae, Polistinae, and Vespinae) were reported in this study. The majority of vespid wasps were reported from subfamily Eumeninae. 5 species of sphecid wasps under 4 genera in 3 subfamilies are reported from Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. 3 sphecid subfamilies reported in this study are Ammophilinae, Sceliphrinae, and Sphecinae. All sphecid wasps were collected from the Malappuram district. Among 5 species of sphecid wasps, *Ammophila clavus*

Fabricius were obtained only from Adyanpara. *Chalybion bengalense* Dahlbom was collected from human residents, especially from undisturbed corners of walls and roofs. *Sphex argentatus* Fabricius is collected from Mini Ooty, which is high altitude area. All collected sphecid wasps were females. They are predators of spiders. There will be more sphecids in Malappuram and Kozhikode districts to get identified. So well established data will be helpful to control many arthropods.

Systematic Account

Family VESPIDAE

Subfamily Eumeninae

Genus *Antepiponade* Saussure, 1855

1. *Antepipona biguttata* Fabricius, 1787 (figure 1)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Thadapparamb, 24.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), China, Korea, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Taiwan, Thailand & Vietnam.

2. *Antepipona ovalis* de Saussure, 1853

Material examined: India: 1 male, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 21.X.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Odisha, Pondicherry, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), Afghanistan, Bangladesh, China & Sri Lanka.

3. *Antepipona rufescens* Smith, 1857 (figure 2)

Material examined: India: 4 male, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Kerala, Meghalaya, Sikkim & Tripura), China, Thailand, Myanmar, Laos, Malaysia and Indonesia (Java (including Kangean), Sumatra, Sulawesi, Moluccas).

Genus *Antodynerus* de Saussure, 1855

4. *Antodynerus flavescens flavescens* Fabricius, 1775 (figure 3)

Material examined: India: 1 male & 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Pondicherry, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal) & Bangladesh.

5. *Antodynerus punctatipennis* de Saussure, 1853 (figure 4)

Material examined: India: 1 male, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 09.VII.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Sikkim, Uttarakhand & Uttar Pradesh).

Genus *Apodynerus* Giordani Soika, 1993

6. *Apodynerus troglodytes troglodytes* de Saussure, 1856 (figure 5)

Material examined: India: 1 male, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 06.VII.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andaman Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Kerala & West Bengal), Borneo, China, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand & Vietnam.

Genus *Delta* de Saussure, 1855

7. *Delta esuriens esuriens* Fabricius, 1787

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Mini Ooty, 22.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Mauritius, Laos, Oman, Pakistan, Qatar, Myanmar, New Caledonia, Philippines, Saudi Arabia, Sri Lanka, Thailand & United Arab Emirates.

8. *Delta pyriforme pyriforme* Fabricius, 1775

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 21.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Pondicherry, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand,

Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), Bhutan, Cambodia, China, Hawaii, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Moluccas, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand & Vietnam.

Genus *Epsilon* de Saussure, 1855

9. *Epsilon chikmagalurensis* Lambert, 2008 (figure 6)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 04.VI.21, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 male, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 17.VI.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala & Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Eumenes* Latreille, 1802

10. *Eumenes belli* Giordani Soika, 1973 (figure 7)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 14.VII.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Karnataka & Kerala).

Genus *Phimenes* Giordani Soika, 1992

11. *Phimenes flavopictum continentale* Zimmermann (figure 9)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 18.X.20, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 26.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand & West Bengal), China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Nepal, Myanmar, Singapore, Thailand & Vietnam.

Genus *Rhynchium* Spinola, 1806

12. *Rhynchium brunneum brunneum* Fabricius, 1793

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 03.XII.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand & West Bengal), Bangladesh, China, Cambodia, Guam, Laos, Malaysia, Marianas, Myanmar, Indonesia, Palau, Seychelles, Thailand & Vietnam.

Subfamily Polistinae

Genus *Polistes* Latreille

13. *Polistes (Polistella) stigma tamulus* Fabricius, 1798 (figure 10)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Pondicherry, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), Pakistan & Sri Lanka.

14. *Polistes (Polistella) strigosus atratus* Das & Gupta (figure 11)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 03.XII.20, Coll. Fahis, India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 28.X.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Kerala, Manipur, Sikkim, Tripura, Uttarakhand & West Bengal).

Genus *Ropalidia* Guerin

15. *Ropalidia brevita* Das & Gupta, 1989 (figure 12)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 04.V.21, Coll. Fahis, India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Mini Ooty, 16.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal) & Pakistan.

16. *Ropalidia stigma* Smith (figure 14)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 31.III.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Jharkhand, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Sikkim, Tripura, Uttarakhand & West Bengal), China, Indonesia (Bali, Borneo, Java & Sumatra), Malay Peninsula, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand & Vietnam.

Subfamily Vespinae

Genus *Vespa* Linnaeus

17. *Vespa affinis continentalis* Bequaert (figure 15)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 11.X.20, Coll. Fahis, India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 04.V.21, Coll. Fahis. & India: 1 female, Kerala, Kozhikode, Koorottupara, 28.VI.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Bihar, Kerala, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu & West Bengal), China, Indonesia, Myanmar, Sri Lanka & Taiwan.

18. *Vespa tropica haematodes* Bequaert, 1936 (figure 16)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 17.X.20, Coll. Fahis, India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 27.X.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Odisha, Pondicherry, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand & West Bengal), China, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka & Vietnam.

Family SPHECIDAE

Subfamily Ammophilinae

Genus *Ammophila* Kirby

19. *Ammophila clavus* Fabricius, 1775 (figure 17)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Adyanpara, 29.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Kerala, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), Australia, Indonesia, China, Japan, Laos & Nepal.

Subfamily Sceliphrinae

Genus *Chalybion* Dahlbom, 1843

20. *Chalybion bengalense* Dahlbom, 1845 (figure 18)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 03.X.20, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 05.I.21, Coll. Fahis

Distribution: India (Kerala, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh & West Bengal), South Africa, Tanzania, Madagascas, Mascarenes, Seychelles islands, Ethiopia, Yemen, Maldives, Socotra, Eritrea, Mozambique, Bangladesh, Iraq, Egypt, Greece, Nepal, Italy, French Polynesia, Sri Lanka, Burma, Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, China, Taiwan, Japan, Volcano Island, Philippines, Borneo, Java, Indonesia, Ternate, Misool, Sulawesi, Timor, Gilbert Island, Guam Island, Lesser Sunda Island, Chagos Archipelago, Australia, United State and Vietnam.

Genus *Sceliphron* Klug, 1801

21. *Sceliphron madraspatanam madraspatanam* Fabricius, 1781 (figure 19)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 03.X.20, Coll. Fahis., India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, PSMO College, 29.V.21, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Pondicherry, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Maldives, Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, Cambodia, Malaysia & Indonesia.

Subfamily Sphecinae

Genus *Sphex* Linnaeus

22. *Sphex argentatus* Fabricius, 1787 (figure 20)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Mini Ooty, 14.IX.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Assam, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal), Angola, Australia, Cambodia, Dableeh island, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Indonesia, Japan, North America, New Guinea, Philippines, Thailand, China, Hong Kong, Australia, Benin, Botswana, Egypt, Kenya, Kuwait, Laos, Malawi, Myanmar, Malaysia, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Sudan, Benin, Botswana, Taiwan, Tanzania, Zambia, Zaire, Zimbabwe, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Seychelles islands, Spain, Sudan, Sri Lanka, South Africa, Kazakhstan, Korea, Uganda, Namibia, Yemen & Pakistan.

23. *Sphex subtruncatus* Dahlbom (figure 21)

Material examined: India: 1 female, Kerala, Malappuram, Arimbra, 11.X.20, Coll. Fahis.

Distribution: India (Sikkim, West Bengal, Meghalaya, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Kerala, and the Western Ghats), Indonesia, China, Africa, Myanmar & Sri Lanka.

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PLATE 1

1. *Antepipona biguttata* (Fabricius)

2. *Antepipona rufescens* (Smith)

3. *Antodynerus flavescens flavescens* (Fabricius)

4. *Antodynerus punctatipennis* (deSaussure)

5. *Apodynerus troglodytes troglodytes* (Lambert)

6. *Epsilon chikmagalurensis* (de Saussure)

PLATE 2

7. *Eumenes belli* (GiordaniSoika)

8. Dorsalview of *Eumenes belli*

9. *Phimenes flavopictum continentale*
(Zimmermann)(Fabricius)

10. *Polistes (Polistella) stigma tamulus*

11. *Polistes (Polistella) strigosus atratus*
(Das & Gupta)

12. *Ropalidia brevita*
(Das & Gupta)

PLATE 3

13. Nest of *Ropalidia brevita*

14. *Ropalidia stigma* (Smith)

15. *Vespa affinis continentalis* (Bequaert)

16. *Vespa tropica haematodes* (Bequaert)

17. *Ammophila clavus* (Fabricius)

18. *Chalybion bengalense* (Dahlbom)

PLATE 4

19. *Sceliphron madraspatanam madraspatanam* (Fabricius)

20. *Sphex argentatus* (Fabricius)

21. *Sphex subtruncatus* (Dahlbom)